

QUALITY MANAGEMENT OF ADDITIONAL EDUCATIONAL SERVICES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation

In the article, the problematic issues of quality management of additional education services for children of preschool education organization are defined and based. The author reveals the conflict between the objective need to form an effective system of additional education quality management and the insufficient development of this problem in the theory and practice of additional education services for children of preschool educational organizations. Additional educational services in pre-school educational institutions are a type of educational circles that implement various types of educational programs and services that go beyond the basic educational program (strict educational standard) for the benefit of the individual, society and the state. The resolution of the conflict consists in the development and implementation of a quality management model of additional educational services for the preschool educational organization. The main tasks of additional educational services for the children of the preschool educational organization are the development of motivation for knowledge and creativity and, ultimately, well-rounded, comprehensively developed, creative, free and unique. child is to solve the problem of personality formation.

Key words: preschool education, organization, additional education, services, criteria, quality of education, management, control, monitoring, demand, customer, executive, child personality, unique, metabolism, activity, microclimate, early childhood, management.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of the rapid changes taking place in our country, new requirements are being imposed on the system of additional educational services in the preschool education organization. In general, the field of education, in particular, is considered as the field of providing additional education services to the pupils of preschool education organizations (specific services related to the formation of a unique child's personality, increase of intellectual resources, transfer of cultural values). Therefore, the process of modernization of the educational system helps to become subjects of additional educational services for children of preschool educational organization. It follows that in modern conditions, the problem of quality management of additional educational services for children of preschool education organization is of particular importance.

The quality of education is a set of important features and characteristics of educational results that can meet the needs of students themselves, society and customers for additional education. The most common assessment of the quality of preschool education is its compliance with accepted state educational standards. The educational process in all pre-school educational institutions of the educational system should be subject to state standards

as uniform norms or standards. For us, the state standard is, first of all, a requirement, an instruction, and it must be fulfilled. It is in this sense that the standard should be understood as a mandatory minimum. The legal paradox of additional educational services for children of preschool education organization is that it is subject to general state standards as an integral part of the general preschool education system, but as an independent type of education, it is determined by goals and tasks. On the one hand, additional education services are organized by MTT based on the organization's capabilities, as well as taking into account the interests of children, families and the local community. Provision of additional educational services in preschool educational organizations is carried out in accordance with the current regulatory and legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan. That is, in accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 30, 2018 No. PQ-3955 "On measures to improve the management of the preschool education system" On the basis of the order of the Ministry of Pre-school Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated December 13, 2018 No. 3 "Organization of additional additional educational and educational services in state preschool educational organizations", "Organization of additional additional educational and educational services in state preschool educational organizations" "On the procedure" and in accordance with its charter.

Additional education services are optional and can be organized by volunteers, parents, professionals and sponsors. Additional educational services are provided outside of the main educational activities and are not included in the MTT curriculum. Pedagogues, volunteers, sponsors, specialists, parents who provide additional education services develop a thematic plan, which, depending on the provision of services, can be made on the basis of the annual thematic plan of the state curriculum¹. On the other hand, "the content of the activity is determined by the customer and the contractor"². Thus, quality management of additional educational services in preschool educational institutions in modern conditions requires special approaches, features of the educational environment, additional educational programs of various directions, and non-standard solutions that fully take into account the requirements and needs of parents and other social partners.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

At the moment, the analysis of literature and Internet sources shows that the quality of pedagogical research in general education (V.P. Panasyuk, M.M. Potashnik, V.A. Kalney, S.E. Shishov, etc.), primary and secondary vocational education (N.N. Bulinskiy, A.T. Glazunov) Sufficient attention is paid to management problems. . I. B. Edakova, T. I. Overchuk and others). But as for the quality of additional education services for preschoolers, this problem has recently come to the attention of researchers. Thus, N.F. Rodionova and M.R. Katunova studied the problem of evaluating the effectiveness of the implementation of additional educational programs based on a competency-based approach³.

¹ State curriculum for preschool educational organizations of the Republic of Uzbekistan (improved second edition) Tashkent-2022.

² Based on the order of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 13, 2018 No. 3 "Organization of additional additional educational and educational services in state preschool educational organizations" "Organization of additional additional educational and educational services in state preschool educational organizations" on the procedure" regulation

³ Evaluating the effectiveness of additional educational programs for children: a competency-based approach: Methodological recommendations / Ed. prof. N. F. Rodionova and. M. R. Katunova. Saint-Petersburg: Publishing House of State Educational Institution "SPb GDTU", 2005

L.G.Loginova conducted a study showing the factors and conditions for achieving the quality of additional education at the level of the regional education system. At the same time, no other specific studies have been conducted on the problem of quality management of education at the local level. At the same time, research conducted in recent years has shown the need to search for new approaches to ensuring the quality of education in preschool educational institutions.

According to generally accepted international standards, quality management includes the evaluation of indicators according to three main quality characteristics:

1. Indicators of investment in additional education, providing it with resources (personnel, legal, informational, financial, material).
2. Quality indicators of the educational process (additional educational programs).
3. Indicators of additional education results in accordance with the requirements of additional education programs.

The proposed evaluation indicators make it possible to create a system of statistics and monitoring of additional education services for children in preschool educational institutions. Monitoring the quality of additional education services requires the integration of all indicators of the quality of additional education services that describe the system "at the entrance", "in the process", "at the exit". This allows to determine the essence of additional educational services of the observed relations, to analyze the processes and their results, to plan the investment of the necessary resources. Identified trends in the state of additional education services make it possible to make correct and timely management decisions that contribute to its further development.

An invariable description of the quality of additional educational services in a preschool educational organization can be obtained based on an assessment of the set of services offered, their variety and compliance with the customer's needs; quality of services (quality of additional education programs, level of teaching, quality of results); the availability of services, the real possibility of using them; quality of service (quality of interaction between additional education pedagogues and students in the field of education, nature of communication and relations, comfortable environment). Quality management ensures a certain level of responsibility for how the quality policy of additional education services in the preschool education organization is formulated, how realistic it is and how consistently it is implemented. In the concept of development of additional education for children in Kuyichirchik district of Tashkent region, "each preschool educational organization should include all quality components of additional educational services, including the conditions designed to ensure the quality of additional educational services, as well as an organizational mechanism for managing the quality of additional educational services. should have a quality management program. But today, instead of such programs, annual thematic rajas are used in the district. The obstacle to the implementation of new approaches is, first of all, the existing organizational and pedagogical culture in the organization of preschool education. The research conducted among the pupils of the additional education system in Kuychichirchik district shows that additional education for children made it possible to determine the following characteristics of the organization's organizational and pedagogical culture:

- unification of the structure of the students, their acceptance of mutual education.
- The values and goals of MTT, the feeling of being a big friendly family, antipathy and rejection of the problem of quality management of educational services.

The need for these characteristics to become a subject of the market of additional educational services in the preschool education organization. As a result, it contradicts the need to develop the organizational and pedagogical culture of the preschool educational organization, which is characterized by its orientation to the external environment. Desire to win in the domestic and additional educational services market and, accordingly, to ensure the quality of these services. The second obstacle to the implementation of new approaches is that scientific research on the quality of additional educational services does not fully take into account the modern features of implementing educational programs aimed at meeting the needs of various consumers - parents, children, MTTs.

The third obstacle is that additional educational services in preschool education organizations, as a rule, implement educational programs of different directions, each of which has its own content and goals. This, in turn, determines the presence of a variable component in the quality management model of additional educational services in a preschool educational organization that implements educational programs of various directions. Thus, a conflict was identified between the objective need to form an effective system for the management of the quality of additional educational services in preschool educational organizations and the lack of development of this problem in the theory and practice of additional educational services for children. It is necessary to justify the management model. Based on the above-mentioned characteristics of the quality management of additional educational services in a preschool education organization, it can be assumed that the quality management model in a preschool education organization includes the following components:

1. In the content of the activity: an invariant component for the educational program implemented in the preschool educational organization (providing additional education with resources; quality of the educational process; additional educational results);

- a variable component of educational quality management that reflects the characteristics of the implementation of additional educational services in various directions.

2. In the evaluation of activity results: development and application of criteria and performance indicators for the implementation of additional educational services in accordance with the fixed and variable components of the content of the model.

Quality management of additional educational services is carried out not only within the framework of the district preschool educational organization, but also at other regional, district and city levels: This means that the quality management model in the preschool educational organization cannot and should not perform all the various tasks of quality management of additional educational services. The main process for the quality management model of additional educational services at the regional, regional and city levels is the management process. Understanding the purpose, role and place of additional educational services in the preschool education system is related to the problem of assessing the quality of the results of activities.

In educational activities, they are vaguely understood. Some additional education services provide students with a learning process similar to school classes. Others see the goal of early childhood education in organizing children's communication in a unique way, not as in MTT. For, "Any adequate conception of educational practice must be broad enough to include the creation of a learning environment for play and inquiry." said Sirai-Blatchford. Still others, when talking about additional educational services, it means forgetting about the

traditional education process in general, not just raising children. Such different positions of pedagogues determine different approaches to seeing the results of additional educational services. If we talk about the current and final achievements of students in the field of additional education, we can distinguish at least three groups of parameters that should be monitored: educational, personal and socio-pedagogical. Each of the parameters can be prioritized in a particular group of children, depending on their characteristics. Generalization of these approaches to the evaluation of the quality of the results of the implementation of additional educational services allowed us to develop a questionnaire and conduct a survey among pedagogues who provide additional educational services in Kuyichirchik district.

RESULTS

The purpose of the study was to select fixed and variable criteria of the effectiveness of the implementation of quality management of additional educational services in a preschool educational organization. By invariant criteria, we understand the criteria that can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of the implementation of quality management of any type of additional education services. Under variable criteria, there are criteria that can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of quality management of additional education services in a specific area.

Questionnaire

Dear colleague! We ask you to participate in the research on the selection of fixed and variable criteria for the effectiveness of the implementation of additional educational services in the preschool educational organization. Your participation and answers are very important in determining the specific criteria for the management of the quality of additional educational services in the preschool educational organization.

The first column of the table below lists the performance parameters for the implementation of quality management of additional education services, and the second column lists the corresponding fixed and variable criteria.

Put the word "and" in front of the criterion if you think it is a fixed criterion, and put the word "in" if you think it can be a variable criterion of the effectiveness of the quality management of additional education services you are implementing. If any criterion gives you difficulty, put "-" next to it. tick.

Table 1.

Parameters of effectiveness of quality management of additional education services	Fixed and variable criteria of effectiveness of quality management of additional education services	"and", "in" or "-"
Scientific achievements: 1. Children's level of mastering the content of additional educational services	mastering the main elements of the content (rules, terms, technologies, etc.) (knowledge, understanding, identification and application ability); students have metabolism, that is, knowledge about knowledge (techniques and means of "discovering" new knowledge); the ability to perform work according to a	

	<p>sample, build an algorithm of one's actions and apply knowledge on the subject in different situations; independent practical work of students; the ability to analyze and process any type of information; comparing visual and verbal forms of presenting material; choose the optimal form for your answer or problem solving;</p> <p>participation of children in learning; the ability to create new types of your own original tasks;</p> <p>the number of pupils who have fully mastered additional education services;</p> <p>quality of children's creative "product" (product, performance, etc.): literacy, artistic and technical level of performance, use of creative elements;</p> <p>stability of students' practical achievements: victories and participation in various contests, festivals, competitions, etc.</p>	
2. Stability of children's interest in taught activities, offered activities and team	<p>current and future security of the contingent;</p> <p>positive motives for participation in activities;</p> <p>children's understanding of the social importance of the topic (activity and community);</p> <p>assessment of the role of the object in the child's future plans;</p> <p>wide application of knowledge by students;</p>	
<p>Personal achievements:</p> <p>1. The direction of the dynamics of personal changes</p>	<p>the nature of changes in personal qualities, the direction of the child's position in life and work;</p> <p>the nature of life values;</p> <p>age appropriateness of worldviews and worldviews</p>	
2. Ethical development of students (orienting children to moral values)	<p>the nature of the relationship between the pedagogue and children, between members of the children's team;</p> <p>the state of the microclimate in the group;</p> <p>the nature of the orientations and</p>	

	<p>motivations of each child and of the community as a whole; behavioral culture of children</p>	
<p>3. The level of creative activity of children</p>	<p>existence of a search, inventive and creative activity system for children; children's mood and position in creative activity (desire - reluctance, satisfaction - dissatisfaction); emotional comfort (or discomfort) in performing a non-standard task; not being afraid to make mistakes in expressing one's opinion and point of view; presence of children studying outside of the program or outside of the specified periods of the educational course; the presence of creative products created by children outside the classroom; children's activity in the educational process and other activities; the priority of children's reproductive or creative activity in the educational process</p>	
<p>4. Assessment of the quality of the level of practical implementation of creative achievements of students</p>	<p>level of stability of creative achievements in terms of time and quality; dynamics of development of each child and the community as a whole; diversity of creative achievements: scope, level of complexity, course content classes and types of activities according to the number of children with creative achievements; children's satisfaction with their achievements, objectivity of self-assessment</p>	
<p>Social and pedagogical results</p>	<p>appropriateness of behavior, children's choice of positions in relationships and decision-making in various situations; reduction of morbidity, absence of negative changes in the state of health, formation of a healthy lifestyle; interaction with family; professional description of children; adapting children to market conditions</p>	

DISCUSSION

The conducted research made it possible to obtain the following results. according to pedagogues, the invariable criteria of the "academic achievements" parameter can be:

- ✓ mastering the main elements of the content (rules, terms, technologies, etc.) (knowledge, understanding, identification and application ability);
- ✓ children have metabolism, ie. knowledge about knowledge (techniques and means of "discovering" new knowledge);
- ✓ the ability to perform work according to a sample, build an algorithm of one's actions and apply knowledge on the subject in different situations; independent practical work of children;
- ✓ ability to analyze and process any type of information; comparing visual and verbal forms of presenting material; choose the optimal form for your answer or problem solving;
- ✓ stability of children's practical achievements: victories and participation in various contests, festivals, competitions, etc.
- ✓ children understand the social significance and importance of the topic (activity and community);
- ✓ assessment of the role of the object in the child's future plans;
- ✓ wide application of knowledge by children in practice;
- ✓ Fixed criteria of "Personal achievements" parameter:
- ✓ age appropriateness of worldview, worldview and worldview;
- ✓ the nature of the relationship between the teacher and the children, between the members of the children's team;
- ✓ state of microclimate in the group;
- ✓ nature of orientations and motives of each child and the community as a whole;
- ✓ behavioral culture of children;
- ✓ existence of a search, inventive and creative activity system for children;
- ✓ not being afraid to make mistakes in expressing one's opinion and point of view;
- ✓ children's activity in the educational process and other activities;
- ✓ the priority of children's reproductive or creative activity in the educational process;
- ✓ level of stability of creative achievements in terms of time and quality; dynamics of development of each child and the community as a whole;
- ✓ diversity of creative achievements: in terms of scope, level of complexity, content of the educational course and types of activities, in terms of the number of children with creative achievements;
- ✓ children's satisfaction with their achievements, objectivity of self-assessment
- ✓ Fixed criteria of "Social-pedagogical results" parameter:
- ✓ Adequacy of behavior, children's choice of positions in relationships and decision-making in various situations;
- ✓ interaction with family;
- ✓ adaptation of children to market conditions.

Such a choice of criteria, firstly, allows the administration to plan work on quality management in the preschool educational organization, secondly, it allows to evaluate the quality management of the results of additional educational services implemented by the children themselves, and thirdly, it becomes a certain condition for creation. Each pre-school

organization has a unique set of characteristics that guarantees an unlimited variety of additional educational services content. They have a legal right to it, but in order to develop the system of additional educational services for children, to manage the quality of its activity, it is necessary to create a mechanism to ensure not only stabilization of the achieved situation, integrity and unity in diversity. . The basis for this can be the accepted concrete criteria of the effectiveness of the implementation of additional education services as a result of the agreement of all subjects, and thus a recognized social norm in the context of the idea of lifelong education.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that the problematic issues of quality management of additional education services identified in this article do not exhaust all their diversity. It seems that this problem can be the basis for conducting prospective educational management researches of scientific and theoretical importance. The practice of introducing the quality management model of additional educational services helps to develop preschool educational organizations in the modern conditions of the market of educational services and the competitive environment.

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